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2 **Supporting Information for**

3 **Ocean warming drives abrupt declines in fish productivity at global scale**

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Table S1. Productivity trajectory according to the classification.

Stock name	Species	Large Marine Ecosystem	Class	Trajectory	Shift year	Shift magnitude
ACADRED2J3K	Sebastes fasciatus	Labrador - Newfoundland	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ACADREDUT3	Sebastes fasciatus	Scotian Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ACMACKSARG	Scomber colias	Patagonian Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
ALBAMED	Thunnus alalunga	Mediterranean Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ALBANATL	Thunnus alalunga	North Atlantic Ocean	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
ALPLAICBSAI	Pleuronectes quadrituberculatus	East Bering Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1981	-0.06
ALSKABSAI	Bathyraxa parmifera	East Bering Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	1980	0.05
AMPL23K	Hippoglossoides platessoides	Labrador - Newfoundland	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
AMPL3LNO	Hippoglossoides platessoides	Labrador - Newfoundland	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1983	-0.18
ANCHMEDGSA17-18	Engraulis encrasicolus	Mediterranean Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ANCHMEDGSA6	Engraulis encrasicolus	Mediterranean Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
ANCHOBAYB	Engraulis encrasicolus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ANCHOSA	Engraulis encrasicolus	Agulhas Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
APOLLNSJ	Theragra chalcogramma	Sea of Japan	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
APOLLPJPN	Theragra chalcogramma	Kuroshio Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ARFLOUNDBSAI	Atheresthes stomias	East Bering Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
ARFLOUNDGA	Atheresthes stomias	Gulf of Alaska	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
ARFLOUNDPACOAST	Atheresthes stomias	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
ARGANCHONARG	Engraulis anchoita	Patagonian Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2000	-0.24
ARGANCHOSARG	Engraulis anchoita	Patagonian Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ARGHAKENARG	Merluccius hubbsi	Patagonian Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
ARGHAKESARG	Merluccius hubbsi	Patagonian Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
ATKABSAI	Pleurogrammus monopterygius	East Bering Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
AUROCKPCOAST	Sebastes aurora	California Current	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
AUSSALMONNZ	Arripis trutta	New Zealand Shelf	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
BGRDRNSWWA	Macruronus novaezelandiae	South West Australian Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
BGROCKPCOAST	Sebastes melanostomus	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
BIGEYECWPAC	Thunnus obesus	North Pacific Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
BIGHTREDSE	Centroberyx gerrardi	South West Australian Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
BLACKOREOWECR	Allocyttus niger	New Zealand Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1980	0.01
BLACKROCKCAL	Sebastes melanops	California Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	2009	0.11
BLACKROCKKORECOAST	Sebastes melanops	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
BLACKROCKWASH	Sebastes melanops	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
BLKMARLINIO	Istiompax indica	Indian Ocean	abrupt	increase abrupt	2004	0.07
BLSHARIO	Prionace glauca	Indian Ocean	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
BLUEFISHATLC	Pomatomus saltatrix	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
BLUEROCKCAL	Sebastes mystinus	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
BMACKECS	Scomber australasicus	East China Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
BMARLINATL	Makaira nigricans	South Atlantic Ocean	abrupt	increase abrupt	1976	0.07
BMARLINIO	Makaira mazara	Indian Ocean	abrupt	increase abrupt	1989	0.1
BOCACBCW	Sebastes paucispinis	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1982	-0.05
BOCACGSPCOAST	Sebastes paucispinis	California Current	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
BRMSOJ	Dentex tumifrons	Sea of Japan	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
BRNROCKPCOAST	Sebastes auriculatus	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
BSBASSMATLC	Centropristis striata	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
BSBASSATL	Centropristis striata	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1986	-0.16
BWHITNEA	Micromesistius poutassou	Barents Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CABEZORECOAST	Scorpaenichthys marmoratus	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
CABEZSCAL	Scorpaenichthys marmoratus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
CALSCORPSCAL	Scorpaena guttata	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
CAPENOR	Mallotus villosus	Barents Sea	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
CHAKESA	Merluccius capensis	Benguela Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1989	-0.07
CHILISPCOAST	Sebastes goodei	California Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2004	-0.04
CHROCKPCOAST	Sebastes nebulosus	California Current	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
CHROCKNPCOAST	Sebastes nebulosus	Gulf of Alaska	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
CHROCKSPCOAST	Sebastes nebulosus	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CHTRACCH	Trachurus murphyi	Humboldt Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CMACKPJPN	Scomber japonicus	Kuroshio Current	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
CMACKTSST	Scomber japonicus	East China Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1995	-0.16
COBGM	Rachycentron canadum	Gulf of Mexico	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
COD1F-XIV	Gadus morhua	Greenland Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
COD1IN	Gadus morhua	Canadian Eastern Arctic - West Greenland	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
COD2J3KL	Gadus morhua	Labrador - Newfoundland	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1990	-0.43
COD3NO	Gadus morhua	Labrador - Newfoundland	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
COD3Pn4RS	Gadus morhua	Labrador - Newfoundland	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1985	-0.7
COD4TVn	Gadus morhua	Scotian Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1986	-0.27
COD4X5Yb	Gadus morhua	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
COD5Zjm	Gadus morhua	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1989	-0.31
CODBA2224	Gadus morhua	Baltic Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CODBA2532	Gadus morhua	Baltic Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1987	-0.43
CODFAPL	Gadus morhua	Faroe Plateau	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
CODICE	Gadus morhua	Iceland Shelf and Sea	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
CODIIaW-IV-VIIId	Gadus morhua	North Sea	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
CODIS	Gadus morhua	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
CODNEAR	Gadus morhua	Barents Sea	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
CODVIIek	Gadus morhua	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
CODVla	Gadus morhua	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	quadratic	decrease decelerated	NA	NA
COWCODSCAL	Sebastes levis	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CPRROCKPCOAST	Sebastes caurinus	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CROCKPCOAST	Sebastes pinniger	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CROCKWCVANISOGQCI	Sebastes pinniger	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
CSARDCSCH	Strangomera bentincki	Humboldt Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
CTRACSA	Trachurus capensis	Agulhas Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	1955	0.1
CUSKVa-XIV	Brosme brosme	Greenland Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
DEEPCHAKESA	Merluccius paradoxus	Benguela Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	1962	0.23
DEEPLATHEADSE	Platycephalus conatus	South West Australian Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
DKROCKPCOAST	Sebastes crameri	California Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	1999	0.03
DSOLEGA	Microstomus pacificus	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
DSOLEPCOAST	Microstomus pacificus	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
DUSROCKGA	Sebastes variabilis	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
EBASSIVbc-VII	Dicentrarchus labrax	North Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA

Stock name	Species	Large Marine Ecosystem	Class	Trajectory	Shift year	Shift magnitude
ECSOLEASASC	Austroglossus pectoralis	Agulhas Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1999	-0.02
ESOLEHS	Parophrys vetulus	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
ESOLEPCOAST	Parophrys vetulus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
FLSOLEBSAI	Hippoglossoides elassodon	East Bering Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1991	-0.08
FLSOLEGA	Hippoglossoides elassodon	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
FMEG8c9a	Lepidorhombus boscii	Iberian Coastal	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
GAGSATLC	Mycteroperca microlepis	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1978	0.16
GEMFISHNZ	Rexea solandri	New Zealand Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1982	0.05
GEMFISHSE	Rexea solandri	Southeast Australian Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
GHAL23KLMNO	Reinhardtius hippoglossoides	Labrador - Newfoundland	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1990	-0.2
GHALBSAI	Reinhardtius hippoglossoides	East Bering Sea	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
GOLDREDNEAR	Sebastes norvegicus	Barents Sea	quadratic	decrease decelerated	NA	NA
GOLDREDV-VI-XII-XIV	Sebastes norvegicus	Greenland Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1979	-0.06
GOPHERSPCOAST	Sebastes carnatus	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
GRAMBERGM	Seriola dumerili	Gulf of Mexico	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
GRAMBERSATLC	Seriola dumerili	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
GRNSTROCKPCOAST	Sebastes elongatus	California Current	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
GRSPROCKNCAL	Sebastes chlorostictus	California Current	quadratic	increase decelerated	NA	NA
GRSPROCKSCAL	Sebastes chlorostictus	California Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	1972	0.02
GTRIGGM	Balistes capricus	Gulf of Mexico	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
HAD4X5Y	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HAD5Y	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
HADFAPL	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Faroe Plateau	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
HADICE	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Iceland Shelf and Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HADIS	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HADNEAR	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Barents Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	2005	0.2
HADNS-IIIa-VIa	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	North Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1999	-0.24
HADROCK	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
HADVIIb-k	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HAKENRNT	Merluccius merluccius	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	2007	0.6
HAKESOTH	Merluccius merluccius	Iberian Coastal	abrupt	increase abrupt	2004	0.35
HAKESPPSAF	Merluccius spp	Benguela Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
HERR2224IIa	Clupea harengus	North Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2001	-0.27
HERR2529-32	Clupea harengus	Baltic Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1981	-0.1
HERR30-31	Clupea harengus	Baltic Sea	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
HERR4RSP	Clupea harengus	Labrador - Newfoundland	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HERR4VWX	Clupea harengus	Scotian Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
HERRCC	Clupea pallasii	Gulf of Alaska	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
HERRHG	Clupea pallasii	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1982	-0.27
HERRIsum	Clupea harengus	Iceland Shelf and Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2008	-0.27
HERRNIRS	Clupea harengus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HERRNORSS	Clupea harengus	Norwegian Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
HERRNS-IIIa-VIId	Clupea harengus	North Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HERRNWATLC	Clupea harengus	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HERRPRD	Clupea pallasii	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1964	-0.36
HERRRIGA	Clupea harengus	Baltic Sea	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
HERRSIRS	Clupea harengus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
HERRSOG	Clupea pallasii	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1963	-0.21
HERRVla-VIIBC	Clupea harengus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
HERRWCVANI	Clupea pallasii	Gulf of Alaska	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
HMACKIIa-IVa-Vb-VIa-VII-VIII	Trachurus trachurus	Norwegian Sea	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
JANCHOPJPN	Engraulis japonicus	Kuroshio Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
JANCHOSETO	Engraulis japonicus	Kuroshio Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
JANCHOTSST	Engraulis japonicus	East China Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
JMACKPJPN	Trachurus japonicus	Kuroshio Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
JMACKTSST	Trachurus japonicus	East China Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	1985	0.24
KELPGREENLINGORECOAST	Hexagrammos decagrammus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
LINGCODNPCOAST	Ophiodon elongatus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
LINGODSPCOAST	Ophiodon elongatus	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
LINGVa	Molva molva	Iceland Shelf and Sea	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
LNOSEKAPCOAST	Raja rhina	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
LSTHORNHPCOAST	Sebastes altivelis	California Current	quadratic	increase decelerated	NA	NA
MACKNEICES	Scomber scombrus	Norwegian Sea	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
MACKNWATLSA3-4	Scomber scombrus	Labrador - Newfoundland	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
MEG8c9a	Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis	Iberian Coastal	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
MEGVII-VIIIabd	Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
MENATGM	Brevoortia patronus	Gulf of Mexico	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
MENATLAN	Brevoortia tyrannus	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
MONKGMNGB	Lophius americanus	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
MONKSGBMATL	Lophius americanus	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1992	0.05
MORWONGESE	Nemadactylus macropterus	Southeast Australian Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1984	-0.09
MORWONGWSE	Nemadactylus macropterus	South West Australian Shelf	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
MUTSNAPSATLCGM	Lutjanus analis	Gulf of Mexico	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
NPOUTIIIIa-IV	Trisopterus esmarkii	North Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
NROCKBSAI	Sebastes polyspinis	East Bering Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
NROCKGA	Sebastes polyspinis	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
NRSOLEEBSAI	Lepidopsetta polyxystra	East Bering Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
NRSOLEGA	Lepidopsetta polyxystra	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
NZLINGESE	Genypterus blacodes	Southeast Australian Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1990	0.04
NZLINGLIN6b	Genypterus blacodes	South Pacific Ocean	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
NZLINGLIN72	Genypterus blacodes	New Zealand Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
NZLINGLIN7WC	Genypterus blacodes	New Zealand Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
NZLINGWSE	Genypterus blacodes	South West Australian Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
OFLOUNESG	Paralichthys olivaceus	East China Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1995	-0.13
OROUGHYSE	Hoplostethus atlanticus	South West Australian Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1988	0.04
PACBTUNA	Thunnus orientalis	South Pacific Ocean	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1958	-0.24
PANCHCCH	Engraulis ringens	Humboldt Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PANCHNCHSP	Engraulis ringens	Humboldt Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PANCHPERUNC	Engraulis ringens	Humboldt Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PATGRENADIERCH	Macruronus magellanicus	Humboldt Current	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
PATGRENADIERSARG	Macruronus magellanicus	Patagonian Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1993	0.11
PCEELARGS	Genypterus blacodes	Patagonian Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1996	0.06
PCEELCSCH	Genypterus blacodes	Humboldt Current	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA

Stock name	Species	Large Marine Ecosystem	Class	Trajectory	Shift year	Shift magnitude
PCOELSCH	Genypterus blacodes	Humboldt Current	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
PCODSABCD	Gadus macrocephalus	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PCODAI	Gadus macrocephalus	Aleutian Islands	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
PCODBS	Gadus macrocephalus	East Bering Sea	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
PCODGA	Gadus macrocephalus	Gulf of Alaska	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
PCODWCVANI	Gadus macrocephalus	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PERCHBSAI	Sebastes alutus	East Bering Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	1982	0.04
PERCHHG	Sebastes alutus	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1963	-0.03
PERCHWCVANI	Sebastes alutus	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	increase abrupt	1964	0.03
PHAKEPCOAST	Merluccius productus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PILCHPJPN	Sardinops melanostictus	Kuroshio Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1986	-0.63
PILCHTSST	Sardinops melanostictus	East China Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1987	-0.41
PLAIC7d	Pleuronectes platessa	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PLAICCELT	Pleuronectes platessa	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
PLAICECHW	Pleuronectes platessa	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PLAICIS	Pleuronectes platessa	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
PLAICNS	Pleuronectes platessa	North Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
POLL5YZ	Pollachius virens	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
POLLFAPL	Pollachius virens	Faroe Plateau	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
POLLIEG	Pollachius virens	Iceland Shelf and Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
POLLNEAR	Pollachius virens	Barents Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
POLLNS-VI-Illa	Pollachius virens	North Sea	quadratic	decrease decelerated	NA	NA
POPERCHGA	Sebastes alutus	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
POPERCHPCOAST	Sebastes alutus	California Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	2009	0.05
PSOLEPCOAST	Eopsetta jordani	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
PTOOTHFISHMI	Dissostichus eleginoides	South Pacific Ocean	abrupt	increase abrupt	1998	0.03
RBRMECS	Pagrus major	East China Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	1991	0.03
RBRMSETOE	Pagrus major	Kuroshio Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
RBRMSETOW	Pagrus major	Kuroshio Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
REDFEAUS	Centroberyx affinis	Southeast Australian Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
REDFISHSPP3M	Sebastes spp	Labrador - Newfoundland	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2005	-0.46
REXSOLEGA	Glyptocephalus zachirus	Gulf of Alaska	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
REYEROCKBSAI	Sebastes aleutianus	East Bering Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	2003	0.09
REYEROCKGA	Sebastes aleutianus	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	increase abrupt	1991	0.01
RGROUPTSATL	Epinephelus morio	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
RHERRTSST	Etrumeus teres	Sea of Japan	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
RPORGYSATLC	Pagrus pagrus	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
RSNAPGM	Lutjanus campechanus	Gulf of Mexico	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
RSNAPSATLC	Lutjanus campechanus	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
RSOLEGA	Lepidopsetta bilineata	Gulf of Alaska	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
RSOLEHSTR	Lepidopsetta bilineata	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
RSROCKBCWN	Sebastes proriger	Gulf of Alaska	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
RSROCKBCWS	Sebastes proriger	Gulf of Alaska	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SABLEFEBSAIGA	Anoplopoma fimbria	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SABLEFFCAN	Anoplopoma fimbria	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	increase abrupt	1977	0.05
SABLEFFPCOAST	Anoplopoma fimbria	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SAILATL	Istiophorus albicans	South Atlantic Ocean	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SAILWATL	Istiophorus albicans	South Atlantic Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SARDMEDGSA17-18	Sardina pilchardus	Mediterranean Sea	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
SARDPVIIIc-IXa	Sardina pilchardus	Iberian Coastal	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
SARDSAS	Sardinops sagax	Agulhas Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2001	-0.53
SARDSAW	Sardinops sagax	Benguela Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SARDWSE	Sardinops sagax	South West Australian Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1998	0.22
SAURNWPAC	Cololabis saira	Kuroshio Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SBARSHARATL	Carcharhinus plumbeus	Gulf of Mexico	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
SBELLYROCKPCOAST	Sebastes jordani	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SBT	Thunnus maccoyii	Indian Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SBWHITARGS	Micromesistius australis	Patagonian Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
SBWHITGH	Micromesistius australis	Humboldt Current	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
SEELNSSA1	Ammodytes spp	North Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SEELNSSA2	Ammodytes spp	North Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1996	-0.52
SEELNSSA3	Ammodytes spp	North Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SHCROCKPCOAST	Sebastes zacentrus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SILVERFISHSE	Seriolella punctata	Southeast Australian Shelf	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SKJCIO	Katsuwonus pelamis	Indian Ocean	abrupt	increase abrupt	1989	0.32
SKJCWPAC	Katsuwonus pelamis	North Pacific Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SKJEATL	Katsuwonus pelamis	South Atlantic Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SKJWATL	Katsuwonus pelamis	North Atlantic Ocean	abrupt	increase abrupt	1980	0.55
SMDOGATL	Mustelus canis	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SNAPSAUSNSG	Chrysophrys auratus	South West Australian Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SNAPSAUSSGSV	Chrysophrys auratus	South West Australian Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SNAPSAUSSSG	Chrysophrys auratus	South West Australian Shelf	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SNOWGROUPSATLC	Epinephelus niveatus	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SNROCKPCOAST	Sebastes diploproa	California Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	2001	0.08
SOLECS	Solea solea	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SOLEIlla-2224	Solea solea	North Sea	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
SOLEIS	Solea solea	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
SOLENS	Solea solea	North Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SOLEVIllab	Solea solea	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
SOLEVIId	Solea solea	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SOLEVIle	Solea solea	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1975	0.1
SOUTHHAKECH	Merluccius australis	Humboldt Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
SPANMACKGM	Scomberomorus maculatus	Gulf of Mexico	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SPANMACKSATLC	Scomberomorus maculatus	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SPANMACKSETO	Scomberomorus niphonius	Kuroshio Current	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
SPHAKECH	Merluccius gayi	Humboldt Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1995	-0.07
SPRAT22-32	Sprattus sprattus	Baltic Sea	abrupt	increase abrupt	1987	0.19
SPSDOGPCOAST	Squalus suckleyi	California Current	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SSTHORNHGA	Sebastolobus alascanus	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
SSTHORNHPCOAST	Sebastolobus alascanus	California Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1971	0
STFLOUNNPACOAST	Platichthys stellatus	California Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1987	-0.29
STFLOUNSPACOAST	Platichthys stellatus	California Current	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
STMARLINIO	Kajikia audax	Indian Ocean	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA

Stock name	Species	Large Marine Ecosystem	Class	Trajectory	Shift year	Shift magnitude
STMARLINNEPAC	Kajikia audax	North Pacific Ocean	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
STMARLINSWFO	Kajikia audax	South Pacific Ocean	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
STMARLINWCNPAC	Kajikia audax	North Pacific Ocean	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
SWHITSE	Sillago flindersi	Southeast Australian Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1983	0.1
SWORDEPAC	Xiphias gladius	South Pacific Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SWORDNATL	Xiphias gladius	North Atlantic Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
SWORDNPAC	Xiphias gladius	North Pacific Ocean	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
TIGERFLATSE	Neoplattycephalus richardsoni	Southeast Australian Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
TILEGM	Lopholatilus chamaeleonticeps	Gulf of Mexico	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
TILESATLC	Lopholatilus chamaeleonticeps	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1985	0.08
TREVALLYTRE7	Pseudocaranx dentex	New Zealand Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
VSNAPGM	Rhomboplites aurorubens	Gulf of Mexico	quadratic	increase accelerated	NA	NA
VSNAPSATLC	Rhomboplites aurorubens	Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	increase abrupt	1980	0.1
WANGLVII-VIIIabd	Lophius piscatorius	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
WANGLVIIIc-IXa	Lophius piscatorius	Iberian Coastal	quadratic	decrease decelerated	NA	NA
WHAKE4T	Urophycis tenuis	Scotian Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1983	-0.26
WHAKEGBGOM	Urophycis tenuis	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
WHITNS-VIId	Merlangius merlangus	North Sea	linear	decrease constant	NA	NA
WHITVIIa	Merlangius merlangus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	quadratic	decrease decelerated	NA	NA
WHITVIa	Merlangius merlangus	Celtic-Biscay Shelf	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
WMARLINATL	Tetrapturus albidus	South Atlantic Ocean	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
WPOLLAI	Theragra chalcogramma	Aleutian Islands	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
WPOLLBOGO	Theragra chalcogramma	East Bering Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
WPOLLEBS	Theragra chalcogramma	East Bering Sea	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
WPOLLGA	Theragra chalcogramma	Gulf of Alaska	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1981	-0.16
WPOLLNSO	Theragra chalcogramma	Sea of Okhotsk	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1995	-0.07
WPOLLWBS	Theragra chalcogramma	West Bering Sea	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1987	-0.14
WROCKPCOAST	Sebastes entomelas	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
YEGROUPGM	Epinephelus flavolimbatus	Gulf of Mexico	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
YELLGB	Limanda ferruginea	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	quadratic	stable convex	NA	NA
YELLSNEMATL	Limanda ferruginea	Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf	abrupt	decrease abrupt	1987	-0.75
YEYEROCKGA	Sebastes ruberrimus	Gulf of Alaska	no change	stable constant	NA	NA
YEYEROCKPCOAST	Sebastes ruberrimus	California Current	abrupt	increase abrupt	1976	0.02
YFNCWPAC	Thunnus albacares	North Pacific Ocean	linear	increase constant	NA	NA
YNOSEKACSCH	Zearaja chilensis	Humboldt Current	abrupt	decrease abrupt	2001	-0.01
YSOLEBSAI	Limanda aspera	East Bering Sea	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
YTROCKNPACOAST	Sebastes flavidus	California Current	quadratic	stable concave	NA	NA
YTSNAPSATLCGM	Ocyurus chrysurus	Gulf of Mexico	no change	stable constant	NA	NA

Table S2. Hierarchical partitioning and randomization test outputs for abrupt decreases.

variable	I ^a	J ^b	Total	Z.score ^c
Age_maturity	0.25	-0.23	0.03	-0.37
Length_maturity	0.58	0.11	0.69	0.09
DemersPelag	0.16	-0.15	0.01	-0.5
SST_mean	1.83	0.32	2.15	1.85
SST_change	5.68	0.51	6.19	6.59
ER_mean	0.04	-0.02	0.02	-0.65
ER_change	0.23	0.27	0.5	-0.39
coord_X	0.12	-0.08	0.04	-0.56
coord_Y	0.15	0.07	0.22	-0.52

^a Independent contribution of the predictor to explained variance.

^b Joint contribution to explained variance.

^c Independent contribution Z-score from 999 randomizations. Values in bold indicate statistical significance based on upper 0.95 confidence limit.

Table S3. Hierarchical partitioning and randomization test outputs for abrupt increases.

variable	I ^a	J ^b	Total	Z.score ^c
Age_maturity	3.42	0.77	4.18	4.17
Length_maturity	0.51	1.05	1.56	-0.01
DemersPelag	0.32	0.03	0.35	-0.25
SST_mean	0.33	0.51	0.84	-0.29
SST_change	2.5	0.79	3.29	2.65
ER_mean	2.43	1.18	3.61	2.66
ER_change	5.93	0.72	6.65	6.91
coord_X	1.64	-0.37	1.26	1.55
coord_Y	1.58	2.41	3.99	1.36

^a Independent contribution of the predictor to explained variance.

^b Joint contribution to explained variance.

^c Independent contribution Z-score from 999 randomizations. Values in bold indicate statistical significance based on upper 0.95 confidence limit.

Fig. S1. Distribution of classification quality scores by trajectory class. wAICc expresses how much the best model performs in terms of AICc compared to the others. LOO indicates how robust is the model choice to the removal of individual data points. (1-NRMSE) gives the proportion of variation explained by the model. For time series classified as "no change", (1-NRMSE) values are expected to be close to zero since the best model does not differ from the mean of the time series. Values of wAICc below 0.25 correspond to time series classified as abrupt by the fitting method but not validated as abrupt by the asdetect method.

Fig. S3. Stock productivity trajectories by taxonomic order. (A) The number of stocks of the RAMLDB with biomass time series that were not classified (e.g., length<25 years) is displayed in grey. (B) Total catch worldwide between 1950 and 2022 by taxonomic order based on FAO data. Fish silhouettes come from <https://www.phylopic.org/>

Fig. S4. Relationship between the proportion of stock collapse and SST rate of change between 1950 and 2020 at the level of LMEs. LMEs with less than two stocks were not included. Significant linear regression are drawn with a solid line, and dashed line otherwise.

Fig. S5. Overview and spatial distribution of all productivity trajectory types alongside the temporal distribution of productivity abrupt shifts (PAS). Trajectory classification is based only on AICc comparison of four different models. (A) Overall proportion of all productivity trajectory types, with the inner pie chart indicating trajectory shape and the outer layer specifying the trend. (B) Spatial distribution of all trajectory types by FAO major fishing areas. The size of the charts is indicative of the number of stocks, which are also displayed. (C-D) Temporal distribution of positive (C) and negative PAS (D) (color bars and density) with in gray the coverage (i.e., number of stocks with data available in each year) of the time series classified.

Fig. S6. Pairwise Pearson correlation coefficient between explanatory variables for available stocks, for FishLife traits (A) and for all quantitative traits used in the model (B). Background color in the upper triangle indicate level of correlation, lower triangle show correlation biplots, and density distribution are shown on the diagonal. Acceptable correlation level are below 0.7. All variables except stock centroid coordinates X and Y were scaled as used in models.

Fig. S7. Relationship between PAS and stock collapse at stock level. Collapse is either defined as 10% of the maximum biomass (A-C), 15% (D-F), or 50% of average biomass (G-I). See caption of main text Fig. 4 for more details.

Fig. S8. Generalized additive mixed model (GAMM) coefficient estimates for models accounting for negative (A, C) and positive (B, D) PAS against all other trajectories. (A, B) Classification used consists only in AICc comparison (no confirmation of abrupt shifts) with ER as proxy for fishing intensity. (C, D) Classification used is identical to that in the main text fig. 3 with average and trend in U/U_{MSY} instead of ER. See caption of main text fig. 3 for more details.